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FINAL CONFERENCE REPORT

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Evaluation of zoonotic viral spillover risk on bat guano farms in Cambodia

Introduction: USAID Strategies to Prevent (STOP) Spillover works to reduce zoonotic viral spillover risk in multiple countries, including Cambodia.

Context and Aim: Bat guano farming has been practiced for decades and may represent a high-risk practice. We combined surveys of practices and risk factors with participatory epidemiology and testing of guano, water, food, and surfaces for coronaviruses in bat guano farming communities to better understand spillover risk.

Methods: A participatory surveillance system was developed with national, provincial, and district government collaboration. Results from mixed-methods data collection informed interventions, implemented through an adapted trials of improved practices (TIPs) methodology.

Findings: Guano harvesters and neighbors exhibit low risk perception and protective behaviors and high engagement and awareness of bat behavior. Consistent with previous guano sampling work (e.g. USAID PREDICT), we detected previously sequenced alphacoronaviruses from guano and surfaces, and poultry-associated viruses at farms and on food and food preparation surfaces in guano farming and neighboring households. Participants exhibited high engagement in TIPs. Barriers to implementation were identified and addressed.

Innovative contribution: Surveillance and interventions were successful due to the participatory approach and proactive response to addressing risk-reduction barriers. One Health partners are developing and implementing innovative interface-level syndromic-targeted surveillance to rapidly detect and respond to spillover events in guano farming communities.

Title	First Name	Last Name	Email	Gender	Country	Org.	Position
Mr	Teng	Theara	THEARA.TENG@tetrattech.com	Male	Cambodia	TetraTech ARD	Technical Officer
Dr	Tristan	Burgess	tburgess@centerforwildlifestudies.org	Male	USA	Center for Wildlife Studies	VP Science and Education
Dr	Bruno	Gheresi-Chavez	Bruno.Gheresi_Chavez@tufts.edu ,	Male	USA	Tufts University, Cummings School of Veterinary Medicine	Postdoctoral Fellow
Dr	Daniele	Lantagne	daniele.lantagne@tufts.edu	Female	USA	Tufts University, Friedman School of Nutrition	Research Professor, Feinstein International Center
Mr	Ratana	Chhan	ratanaa.chhan@gmail.com	Male	Cambodia	TetraTech ARD	Country Technical Lead – Food, Water and Air
Dr	Jonathan	Gass	Jonathon.Gass@tufts.edu ,	Male	USA	Tufts University School of Medicine	Assistant Professor Public Health and Community Medicine
Dr	Veasna	Duong	dveasna@pasteur-kh.org ,	Male	Cambodia	Institut Pasteur du Cambodge	Head of Virology Unit
Ms	Thavry	Hem	hthavry@pasteur-kh.org ,	Male	Cambodia	Institut Pasteur du Cambodge	Field Study Coordinator
Dr	Felicia	Nutter	Felicia.Nutter@tufts.edu ,	Female	USA	Tufts University, Cummings School of Veterinary Medicine	Assistant Professor, Department of Infectious Disease and Global Health

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